

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman^{1,2}, S.H. Foord², C.R. Haddad³ & E. le Roux⁴

¹ ARC – Plant Health and Protection, Private Bag X134, Queenswood 0121, South Africa; DippenaarA@arc.agric.za

² Department of Zoology, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa

³ Department of Zoology & Entomology, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, South Africa

⁴ Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, Newlands, Cape Town, South Africa

ABSTRACT

An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the Bontebok National Park (BNP) is provided. The checklist was compiled from data collected from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) database. A total of 184 species from 44 families and 134 genera are presently protected in the park. The most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (26 spp.), Salticidae (20 spp.) and Araneidae (19 spp.), while 19 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism and conservation status for each species is provided. Eighty-one of the species have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern. Approximately 8 % of the total South African spider fauna is protected in the Bontebok National Park, and 20 % of the species recorded are South African endemics and 11.4 % are Western Cape endemics. This study provides baseline data on spiders conserved in the Bontebok National Park, which can be used for Red Listing and future assessments of habitat transformation. Only 15 spider species was previously listed from the park and 169 species are newly recorded. Species of special concern are identified, as well as possible new species.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), conservation, endemism, fynbos

INTRODUCTION

As signatories to the Convention on Biodiversity, South Africa is obliged to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable utilization of our species-rich fauna and flora. The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) was initiated in 1997 with the main aim to discover, describe and make an inventory of the South African arachnid fauna. Species distribution data is essential information needed for the conservation assessments to compile a Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa, to have a record of endemic species, and species that are already receiving some protection in existing reserves and parks (McGeoch *et al.* 2011). These species distribution records formed the basis of the first spider atlas and national species list (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010). With continued surveys and new taxonomic data, an updated species list with new information is available.

In South Africa, the Western Cape Province is one of the better sampled provinces, with 966 known species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). However, several areas in the province are still undersampled, and only a few spider checklists of spiders in protected areas have been published: Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2005), Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1999), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). The current study presents the results of data from the SANSa database on the spiders sampled in the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape Province. It includes information on the species' global distribution, endemism and conservation status.

METHODS

Study area and period: Bontebok National Park (BNP) is a species-specific national park in South Africa and was established in 1931 to ensure the preservation of the Bontebok. It is the smallest of South Africa's 20 National Parks and has an extent of 27.86 km². The park is part of the Cape Floristic Region, which is a World Heritage Site. Rebelo *et al.* (2006) classified the vegetation of the BNP as Swellendam Silcrete Fynbos, considering it a poorly known vegetation unit that exhibits floristic features of both fynbos and renosterveld, with very high plant species richness (Fig. 2). The BNP is situated approximately 5 km from the town of Swellendam (Fig. 1) in the Western Cape Province (34°02'S, 20°25'E). The BNP is located in the foothills of the Langeberg Mountains and is bordered to the south by the Breede River. The BNP is situated in the winter rainfall region, and the average annual rainfall is 511 mm, of which 59 % falls in winter.

Sampling methods and identification: Spiders were sampled during short surveys undertaken by the arachnologists of the California Academy of Sciences (October 2011) and the National Museum, Bloemfontein (December 2013). The specimens sampled are housed in their respective collections, but copies of the material sampled was included in the SANSa database. More extensive sampling was undertaken by the last author, who was stationed in the park during 2009 and 2010. Specimens were sampled by hand and preserved in 70% ethanol.

Identifications were done in Pretoria and voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria and the National Museum, Bloemfontein. All this data were used to compile the first checklist of the spiders of BNP (Appendix 1). The taxonomy of certain spider families (e.g. Theridiidae) in southern Africa prevented the identification of some specimens to species level. In some families, only immature specimens were collected and therefore impossible to identify to species level.

FIGURE 1: Map showing location of the Bontebok National Park.

FIGURE 2: Habitat types in the Bontebok National Park (Photos: E. le Roux).

Species endemism and conservation: The conservation status of species is important, and as part of the first edition of the Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010) an endemism index was provided for each species. It was calculated based on current distribution, which included six endemism categories, ranging from: 6 = endemic, known only from type locality / one locality only (Bontebok National Park Endemic, BNPE); 5 = known from one province only, wider than type locality (Western Cape Endemic, WCE); 4 = known from two adjoining provinces only; 3 = South Africa, >two provinces or not adjoining (South African Endemic, SAE); 2 = Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers) (Southern African Endemic, STHE); 1 = Afrotropical Region (African Endemic, AE); 0 = Africa and wider (Cosmopolitan, C).

Regarding conservation status, species that were only recorded from immatures or those that represent possible new species or undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE); species known from only one sex, old material and not revised are data deficient either for taxonomic reasons (DDT) or lack distribution data (DD). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3–5 are South African endemics (SAE), and based on their distribution ranges most of them are also LC. The species in categories 5–6 are Western Cape endemics (WCE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 44 families represented by 134 genera and 184 species have been collected from BNP (Table 3; Appendix 1). In the First Atlas of South African Spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010) only 14 species were listed from BNP. Species were also mentioned in the papers of Schütt (1981) and FitzPatrick (2007). The number of species collected is higher than species recorded from the Karoo National Park, where the 38 families were represented by 116 species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1999), but lower than the De Hoop Nature Reserve, where 252 spp. were sampled after five surveys of between two and 12 days in duration.

In this survey, the Gnaphosidae (26 spp.), Salticidae (20 spp.) and Araneidae (19 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Table 1). There was a very high proportion of singleton families (19), i.e. represented by a single species only.

Species endemism and conservation status: Of the 184 species sampled, 17 spp. (9.2 %) are data deficient (DD), i.e. lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while 10 spp. (5.4 %) were not evaluated (NE), indicating possible new species or species only sampled from juveniles (Table 1; Appendix 1). The majority of the species (153 spp., 83.2 %) sampled are listed as being of least concern (LC), 49 species are Africa endemics, while 46 spp. (25 %) are endemic to southern Africa.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Bontebok National Park, with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S) sampled.

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	2	2	Mimetidae	1	1
Amaurobiidae	2	2	Oecobiidae	1	1
Ammoxenidae	1	1	Oxyopidae	1	3
Anapidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	12	19	Philodromidae	3	3
Bemmeridae	2	2	Pholcidae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	2	3	Pisauridae	5	6
Clubionidae	1	3	Salticidae	17	20
Corinnidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	3
Cyrtachenidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	4
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	2	2
Drymusidae	1	1	Sparassidae	3	4
Dysderidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Entypesidae	2	2	Tetragnathidae	2	6
Eresidae	3	3	Theraphosidae	2	3
Gnaphosidae	15	26	Theridiidae	9	13
Hahniidae	1	1	Thomisidae	8	11
Hersiliidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	5	5	Uloboridae	1	1
Liocranidae	1	1	Zodariidae	4	4
Lycosidae	8	13	Zoropsidae	1	1
Migidae	1	1			

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Bontebok National Park.

DISTRIBUTION	SPP.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data deficient (DD)	17	9.2
Not evaluated (NE)	10	5.4
Least concern (LC)	153	83.2
Rare	2	1.1
Near threatened	1	0.6
Vulnerable	1	0.6
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	19	10.3
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	49	26.6
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	46	25
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE)	22	11.9
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	15	8.1
5 – Western Cape endemics (WCE)	21	11.4
6 – Bontebok National Park (BNP)	0	0

TABLE 3: Species of special concern in the Bontebok National Park. Conservation status (STA): DD = data deficient, known from both sexes; DDT = data deficient; LC = Least Concern; RA = Rare; VUL = Vulnerable. Endemism: R = Rare; WCE = Western Cape endemic; NT = Near Threatened.

SPECIES	STA	ENDEMICITY
FAMILY BEMMERIDAE		
<i>Homostola reticulata</i> (Purcell, 1902)	DD	WCE; NT
FAMILY DRYMUSIDAE		
<i>Izithunzi productum</i> (Purcell, 1904)	RA	WCE; R
FAMILY ERESIDAE		
<i>Dresserus collinus</i> Pocock, 1900	DDT	WCE; NT
FAMILY LIOCRANIDAE		
<i>Rhaeboctesis matroosbergensis</i> Tucker, 1920	DD	WCE; NT
FAMILY LYCOSIDAE		
<i>Proevippa lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1903	LC	WCE; R
<i>Pterartoria caldaria</i> Purcell, 1903	DD	WCE; R
<i>Pterartoria polysticta</i> Purcell, 1903	DD	WCE; R
FAMILY MIGIDAE		
<i>Moggridgea terricola</i> Simon, 1903	VUL	under criterion B
FAMILY ENTYPESIDAE		
<i>Hermacha capensis</i> (Ausserer, 1871)	DD	WCE; NT
<i>Lepthercus engelbrechti</i> Ríos-Tamayo & Lyle, 2020	LC	WCE; R
FAMILY SALTICIDAE		
<i>Rumburak bellus</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith 2014	DDT	WCE; R
FAMILY SCYTODIDAE		
<i>Scytodes testudo</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	WCE; NT
FAMILY SELENOPIDAE		
<i>Anyphops lesserti</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	DDT	WCE; R
FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE		
<i>Stasimopus brevipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	DD	WCE; NT
FAMILY THERAPHOSIDAE		
<i>Harpactira cafreriana</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	LC	WCE; NT
<i>Harpactira dictator</i> Purcell, 1902	LC	WCE; NT
<i>Harpactirella domicola</i> Purcell, 1903	DDT	WCE; NT
FAMILY THOMISIDAE		
<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	NT	under criterion B
FAMILY TRACHELIDAE		
<i>Afrocto capensis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	RA	WCE; R
FAMILY ZOROPSIDAE		
<i>Griswoldia robusta</i> (Simon, 1898)	LC	WCE; R

Of the species identified to species level only 58 spp. are South African endemics (Table 1; Appendix 1). There are presently no endemic species known from the BNP, but 22 species from 16 families are Western Cape endemics (SAE-WCE). These species are of special concern due to their small distribution ranges, and more sampling is needed to resolve this. For other species, many need redescriptions or descriptions of the opposite sex (Table 2).

Preliminary investigations into the biodiversity of the invertebrate fauna in South Africa have highlighted the dilemma caused by a lack of baseline information on the ecology and diversity of most arachnid groups (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002). With the ecology and diversity of the spider fauna of South Africa so poorly known, each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species.

CONCLUSION

As signatories to the Convention on Biological Diversity, South Africa is obliged to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable utilization of the diverse and species rich fauna and flora. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. Established parks, such as BNP, can make a substantial contribution towards invertebrate conservation. However, the contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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FIGURE 3: Selected spiders from the Bontebok National Park. (A) *Harpactira cafreriana* (Walckenaer, 1837) (Theraphosidae); (B) *Harpactira dictator* Purcell, 1902 (Theraphosidae); (C) *Harpactirella domicola* Purcell, 1903 (Theraphosidae); (D) *Palystes castaneus* (Latreille, 1819) (Sparassidae); (E) *Anyphops capensis* (Lawrence, 1940) (Selenopidae); (F) *Evippomma squamulatum* (Lycosidae); (G) *Argiope trifasciata* (Forsskål, 1775) (Araneidae); (G) *Simorcus haddadi* Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010 (Thomisidae) (Photos: E. le Roux).

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Bontebok National Park, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution (DIST). * indicates species previously recorded from the park.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
AGELENIDAE	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Pseudauximus pallidus</i> Purcell, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Chresiona</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
AMMOXENIDAE	<i>Ammoxenus pentheri</i> Simon, 1896	2	LC	STHE
ANAPIDAE	<i>Crozetulus rhodesiensis</i> Brignoli, 1981*	2	LC	STHE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Argiope aurocincta</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C
	<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa elongatus</i> (Lawrence, 1947)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C. L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinioides</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C. L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE
	BEMMERIDAE	<i>Homostola reticulata</i> (Purcell, 1902)	5	DD
<i>Spiroctenus validus</i> (Purcell, 1902)		5	DD	SAE
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona ansiae</i> Lotz, 2002*	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona krugerensis</i> Lotz, 2003	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona lawrencei</i> Roewer, 1951	2	LC	STHE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypha</i> sp. (new)		NE	
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Archaeodictyna</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
DRYMUSIDAE	<i>Izithunzi productum</i> (Purcell, 1904)	5	RARE	SAE
DYSDERIDAE	<i>Dysdera crocata</i> C.L. Koch, 1838	0	LC	C
ENTYPESIDAE	<i>Hermacha capensis</i> (Ausserer, 1871)	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Lepthercus engelbrechti</i> Ríos-Tamayo & Lyle, 2020	5	LC	SAE
ERESIDAE	<i>Dresserus collinus</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Aphantaulax stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina pavesii</i> (Simon, 1897)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina procurva</i> (Purcell, 1908)	1	LC	STHE

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leptodrassex</i> sp. (new)		NE	
	<i>Megamyrmaekion schreineri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Poecilochroa involuta</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Prodidomus capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pterotricha auris</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Scotophaeus relegatus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma capensis</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma fusca</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trephopoda kannemeyeri</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907*	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus bicavus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus capensis</i> Purcell, 1907	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes albanicus</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes caldarius</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes humilis</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
HERSILIIDAE	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ceratinopsis dippenaari</i> Jocqué, 1984	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Prinerigone vagans</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
LIOCRANIDAE	<i>Rhaeboctesis matroosbergensis</i> Tucker, 1920	5	DD	SAE
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa faberrima</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Arctosa promontorii</i> (Purcell, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna unicolor</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa manubriata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1903	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Pterartoria caldaria</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Pterartoria polysticta</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
	<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
MIGIDAE	<i>Moggridgea terricola</i> Simon, 1903	5	VU	SAE
MIMETIDAE	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
OECOBIIDAE	<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
PHOLCIDAE	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE

APPENDIX 1: - continued.

PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Lamaika distincta</i> Griswold, 1990	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cispus</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
	<i>Euprosthopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)*	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euprosthopsis lamorali</i> Blandin, 1977	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Nilus curtus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1876	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euophrys leipoldti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Habrocestum luculentum</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus insperatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus pratti</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> (Dufour, 1831)	0	LC	C
	<i>Mexcala rufa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Myrmarachne leleupi</i> Wanless, 1978	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pseudicius africanus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rumburak bellus</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala hirsuta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes flagellata</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer, 1837	0	LC	C
	<i>Scytodes testudo</i> Purcell, 1904	5	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE	<i>Anyphops capensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops hessei</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops lesserti</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	5	DDT	SAE
	<i>Anyphops purcelli</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	4	DD	SAE
SICARIIDAE	<i>Hexophthalma spatulatus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE
	<i>Palystes castaneus</i> (Latreille, 1819)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875*	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes lycosinus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	LC	SAE
STASIMOPIIDAE	<i>Stasimopus brevipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DD	SAE
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C

	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C
	<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872*	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Harpactira cafreriana</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Harpactira dictator</i> Purcell, 1902	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Harpactirella domicola</i> Purcell, 1903	5	DDT	SAE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euryopsis</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841*	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus indistinctus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion delicatum</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3 (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Theridion</i> sp. 4 (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
THOMISIDAE	<i>Avelis hystriculus</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)*	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	5	NT	SAE
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema imitator</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890*	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus havilandi</i> Lawrence, 1942*	3	LC	SAE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afroseto capensis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	5	RARE	SAE
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900*	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Heradida speculigera</i> Jocqué, 1987	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Psammoduon canosum</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
ZOROPSIDAE	<i>Griswoldia robusta</i> (Simon, 1898)	5	LC	SAE

Endemicity (END): (6) only known from the type locality, Bontreboek National Park endemic; (5) endemic to Western Cape Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; WCE, Western Cape endemic.